

Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM diversity-gap reduction

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QUESTIONNAIRE – ENGLISH

GRIAL RESEARCH GROUP (USAL)

CreaSTEAM CONSORTIUM

2023

QUESTIONNAIRE

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Gender:
Female – Male - Not mentioned above - No answer
2. Year of birth:
3. Course (according to the local education system):
4. Country of birth:
5. Country where you are living:
6. Years in the country where you are living:
 - a. less than 6 months
 - b. 6 months – 2 years
 - c. more than 2 years and less than 5 years
 - d. more than 5 years and less than all your life
 - e. all your life
7. Father's level of schooling:
None - Primary education – Secondary Education – Higher Education
8. Father's country of birth:
9. Mother's level of schooling:
None - Primary education – Secondary Education – Higher Education
10. Mother's country of birth:
11. Have you got brothers and/or sisters? How many?
12. Have you previously participated in other activities with your classmates like STEMS?
YES – NO
13. If YES, did you like to participate in the activity? (Dislike very much, Dislike somewhat, Neither like nor dislike, Like somewhat, Like very much)

BLOCK 1 (PRE - POST). Vocational motivation and perception in STEM. Objective: To assess the change in perception and self-perception regarding STEM areas, after the application of the didactic units of the project.

Part I.

This five-part questionnaire is designed to assess your perceptions of scientific disciplines. It should require about 5 minutes of your time. Usually, it is best to respond with your first impression, without giving a question much thought.

Instructions: Choose one circle between each adjective pair to indicate how you feel about the object.

14. To me, SCIENCE is:

fascinating	1	2	3	4	5	mundane
appealing	1	2	3	4	5	unappealing
exciting	1	2	3	4	5	unexciting
means nothing	1	2	3	4	5	means a lot
boring	1	2	3	4	5	interesting

15. To me, MATH is:

fascinating	1	2	3	4	5	mundane
appealing	1	2	3	4	5	unappealing
exciting	1	2	3	4	5	unexciting
means nothing	1	2	3	4	5	means a lot
boring	1	2	3	4	5	interesting

16. To me, ENGINEERING is:

fascinating	1	2	3	4	5	mundane
appealing	1	2	3	4	5	unappealing
exciting	1	2	3	4	5	unexciting
means nothing	1	2	3	4	5	means a lot
boring	1	2	3	4	5	interesting

17. To me, TECHNOLOGY is:

fascinating	1	2	3	4	5	mundane
appealing	1	2	3	4	5	unappealing
exciting	1	2	3	4	5	unexciting
means nothing	1	2	3	4	5	means a lot
boring	1	2	3	4	5	interesting

18. To me, a CAREER in science, technology, engineering, or mathematics (is):

fascinating	1	2	3	4	5	mundane
appealing	1	2	3	4	5	unappealing
exciting	1	2	3	4	5	unexciting
means nothing	1	2	3	4	5	means a lot
boring	1	2	3	4	5	interesting

Source: STEM Semantics Survey

Part II.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
19. I would consider choosing a career that uses math.					
20. I would consider choosing a career that uses science.					
21. I would consider choosing a career that is focused on technology.					
22. I would consider choosing a career in engineering.					
23. I am the type of student to do well in math.					
24. I know I can do well in science.					
25. I believe I can be successful in a career in engineering.					
26. I believe I can be successful in a career in technology.					

Source: Student Attitudes toward STEM Survey-Middle and High School Students

BLOCK 2 (PRE - POST). School climate and inclusive space in the school and with peers and teachers (before and after STEAM Lab implementation).

Category		Not at all	Not much	Neutral	Somehow	A lot	I don't know
Students' perceptions of inclusive practices for entry to school	27. Do you feel welcomed in school?						
Students' perceptions of inclusion within school	28. Are other children friendly with you?						
	29. Are teachers friendly?						
	30. Do you feel included when deciding about class rules?						
	31. When you face difficulties do you get help by other children?						
	32. When you face difficulties do you get help by other teachers?						
	33. Do you attend extra-curricular activities?						
	34. Do you think inclusion is an important element of school policies?						
	35. Do you think school is committed for inclusiveness of all children?						
Students' perception on how much they like the school	36. Do you think, there are physical obstacles to enter school building, eg. Students with special needs?						
	37. How much do you like school?						

Source: Survey on Inclusive Education in ten Primary Schools of Kosovo

BLOCK 3 (POST). SATISFACTION

38. List up to three things (activities, technologies used, content, practical approaches, spaces, teachers) you liked about the activities you participated in.
39. List up to three things (activities, technologies used, content, practical approaches, spaces, teachers) you did not like about the activities you took part in.
40. Give a mark for the activities you took part in.
41. Indicate what would you change for improve the activities for each positive or negative comment that you describe above.